

WORD FORMATION AND ITS REALIZATION IN NEWSPAPER STYLE.

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Annotation: *Word-formation as a means of the language development was widely studied by many linguists, foreign and native. They all agree that word-formation is one of the most important methods of language replenishment and enrichment. «Word-formation is that branch of lexicology which analyzes the derivative structure of existing words and the patterns, on which a language, in this case English, produces new words, according to R.Z. Ginzburg. The quick flow of events, the progress of science and technology, and the formation of new concepts in various domains of human activity may be partly to blame for the appearance of a significant number of new words and the development of new meanings in the words currently accessible in the language. F. Ungerer recognizes, that «word-formation is one of those linguistic terms that may be unsatisfactory on a more theoretical level, but that are immensely useful when one tries to survey processes of extending the lexicon.*

Key words: *English language, lexicology, ways of word-formation, word-formation, blending, conversion, typologies of blending, classes of conversion.*

The world is changing at a rapid pace. Language is no exception: certain terms have become antiquated and are no longer employed in ordinary conversation, but there are many new ones that are widely used. As a result, our vocabularies are evolving as well. The desire to convey new thoughts leads to the formation of new words, which is a result of the advancement of science, technology, and culture. In English, for example, there are numerous methods to form words. For example, blending (documentary + drama = docudrama). Blending is thought to be one of the most current today. Blended word development is a typical approach of word formation with its own set of properties. Blending is the process of combining two or more word fragments into a new linguistic unit. On the Cambridge English Corpus, the definition is "to mix or put together," which helps us visualize a blender for chopping food, preparing mixes, purees, and drinks. As a result, we can deduce that it refers to the process of combining elements of words into a single new word. Blending is the process of

mixing components of two words to create a new term. Blends, often known as fusions or portmanteau words, are a type of blending. It is discussed the process of forming new words by blending and the typology of this method of word formation. Blend is a word construction strategy that became popular in English only in the twentieth century, however some experts believe it existed far earlier. This strategy entails combining two words into a single word. The lexical meanings of both words from which it was derived are included in the resulting construct. Typically, a new unit of speech (or blend) is made up of the first part of one word - "donor" - and the last portion of another. A large number of new and highly capacious terms have formed in the language as a result of this type of word construction, which we can today find in the fields of politics, advertising, and mass media, as well as in ordinary speech. Mostly blends are formed from a word-group, such as: acromania (acronym mania), cinemadict (cinema addict), chunnel (channel, canal), dramedy (drama comedy), detectifiction (detective fiction), faction (fact fiction: fiction based on real facts), informercial (information commercial), Medicare (medical care), magalog (magazine catalogue) slimnastics (slimming gymnastics), sociolite (social elite), slanguist (slang linguist),

In Modern English, conversion is a highly productive means of coining new words. Conversion is also known as affixless word-building, which is the process of creating a new word from an existing root word by altering the category of a part of speech without altering the morphemic structure of the original root-word. Though it might be more or less clearly connected with the old word, the new one has a meaning that is distinct from it. It also has a new paradigm that is unique to its new classification as a part of speech. The problem of semantic origination factors emerges in contexts of conversion: which of the converted pairs is primary and which is converted from it. Prof. A.I. Smirnitsky was the one who initially looked into the problem. Later, P.A. Soboleva refined his concept and established the following criteria: 1. A word is primary if the lexical meaning of the root morpheme and the lexico-grammatical meaning of the stem are the same, as in the situations pen - to pen and father - to father, where the nouns are names of an object and a living creature, respectively. Because the verbs "to pen" and "to father" describe an activity or a process, the stems' lexico-grammatical meanings differ from the roots' lexical meanings. The verbs were transformed from nouns and have a complex semantic structure. 2. We can determine which of the two pairs is principal by comparing a converted pair to a synonymic word pair created through suffixation. Only nouns transformed from verbs can be compared using this criterion; for example, "chat" n. and "chat" v. can be compared to

"conversation" - "converse."3.The derivational relations criterion has a more universal aspect. In this situation, we'll need to find a word-cluster of relative terms that the converted pair belongs to. The noun is primary in the converted pair if the root stem of the word-cluster has suffixes added to a noun stem, and vice versa. For example, in the word-cluster: hand n., hand v., handy, handful, the derived words have suffixes added to a noun stem, so the noun is primary and the verb is converted from it. The basic word in the word-cluster: dance n., dance v., dancer, dancing is a verb, and the noun is converted from it. The term "conversion," which some linguists believe is insufficient, refers to the countless instances of phonetic identity of word-forms, particularly the so-called starting forms, of two words belonging to distinct sections of speech. The following examples can be used to demonstrate this: work-to-work; love-to-love; paper-to-paper; brief-to-brief, and so on. We usually deal with simple words, with a few outliers, such as wireless-to-wireless.

I.V. Arnold understands word-formation as the process of creating new words from the language's resources, or the system of derivative types of words, and the process of creating new words from the language's material after certain structural and semantic formulas and patterns. Word-building, in conjunction with borrowing, allows for the expansion and enrichment of the language's vocabulary.

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